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INDEX OF ECONOMIC FREEDOM: METHODOLOGY AND ANALYSIS IN THE MODERN WORLD ECONOMY

The increasing macroeconomic and geopolitical instability in the modern global economy negatively impacts economic and social processes in various countries, which inevitably leads to an increased role of government administration and regulation, as well as restrictions on economic freedom in society. In this regard, there is a need to revise and modernize methodological approaches to studying such a category as economic freedom, as well as the degree of influence on it not only by state regulation, but also by polycentrism, which is an important trend in the development of the modern global economy. The article presents a model for ensuring the maximum level of economic freedom in a country under conditions of polycentrism and state regulation. and the underlying classification of restrictions on the economic freedom of subjects was also developed. The article also provides a classification of restrictions on the economic freedom of subjects, criteria for classifying a phenomenon as a manifestation of economic freedom under the influence of regulatory procedures and polycentrism, and a subject structure of sources of restrictions on the economic freedom of a subject, as well as basic vectors of state influence on economic freedom. The author's approach to

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the concept of economic freedom is based on the complex and multi-level interactions between government agencies, international organizations, competitive forces, counterparties, and structured market groups.

Keywords: index of economic freedom, government regulation, sanctions pressure, polycentrism.

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 S_r = \sum s_r \rightarrow \min \\
 R_s = \sum r_s \rightarrow \max,
 \end{cases}
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<p>3.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • : • () ; • ; • ; • () ; • - • ; • - 	<p>$C_i = ? c_i/n$</p> <p>$C_i =$ —</p> <p>$c_i =$ — ;</p> <p>$n =$ — ;</p>
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